

PROGNOSTIC CRITERIA FOR CORONARY HEART DISEASE

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Introduction.

Of particular interest are the issues of gender differences in patients with coronary heart disease, an atypical form of angina pectoris. Coronary heart disease is not a linearly progressive, stable process. CHD is characterized by a change of phases of stable course and exacerbation of the disease. In the population, only about 40-50% of all patients are aware of the presence of the disease and receive appropriate treatment, whereas in 50-60% the disease remains unrecognized [1].

Patients diagnosed with stable angina pectoris die from coronary heart disease 2 times more often than those without this disease [2].

The purpose of the study: To study the cytokine status in CHD depending on gender in order to develop criteria for the severity of its course.

Materials and methods of research:

The study included 120 patients with coronary heart disease aged 25 to 85 years (the average age of men was 62.6 ± 1.47 years, and women 63.4 ± 1.14 years). The comparison group consisted of patients with progressive angina pectoris (PS), a total of 65 patients, including 31 women and 34 men (average age 64.2 ± 1.37 years).

The verification of coronary heart disease was carried out according to the requirements of the World Health Organization (WHO), classified according to the international classification of diseases (ICD-10).

The results and their discussion.

The ratio of men-66 (55.0%) and women-54 (45.0%) was 1.2:1.0. A comparative analysis of the frequency of coronary heart disease, taking into account gender, showed an increase in cases of coronary heart disease in men aged 50 years and older - 57 (86.4%), in women aged 50 to 74 years - 44 (81.5%).

The study of cytokines in coronary heart disease showed an increase in the level of IL-1 to 77.6 ± 1.29 pg/ml in relation to the indicators of patients of the comparative and 2nd groups: 60.6 ± 1.14 pg/ml and 65.0 ± 2.12 pg/ml, respectively, $P < 0.05$.

At the same time, the threshold level indicating the development of inflammation in CHD in women is the concentration of IL-1 > 67.0 pg/ml.

CHD in women is also accompanied by a decrease in the level of IL-10 by 1.5 times, against the values of the 2nd group- 43.8 ± 2.19 pg/ml. Consequently, in women, coronary heart disease is accompanied by a decrease in IL-10, while the threshold level is $IL-10 < 6.25$ pg/ml.

It should be noted that IL-10 of the comparative group was reduced to -34.5 ± 0.28 pg/ml, against the indicators of the 2nd group ($p < 0.05$). This means that during the transition of coronary heart disease to PS, there is a decrease in IL-10, which indicates the depletion of the protective mechanisms of immunity.

The study of the state of vascular endothelin factor in coronary heart disease revealed an increase in the concentration of VEGF in men to -104.5 ± 2.15 pg/ml relative to the indicators of group 1- 92.7 ± 3.51 pg/ml ($p < 0.05$). Consequently, in men with coronary heart disease, in response to damage to the vascular wall as a result of impaired microcirculation in the myocardium and spasm of the coronary vessels, there is an increase in vascular endothelin factor in the blood by 1.12 times compared to the values of group 1 (in women).

Thus, in women, coronary heart disease without ST segment elevation occurs against the background of anemia and lymphocytopenia.

A comparative analysis of the studied blood parameters in men, depending on the state of the segment, with coronary heart disease with ST segment elevation showed an increase in the level of Hb to 120.7 ± 1.33 g/l against these men without its elevation -113.9 ± 2.35 g/l. The remaining indicators did not depend on the ST shift and were at the same level in men.

At the same time, for both women and men, the threshold level indicating the development of inflammation in coronary heart disease is the concentration of IL-1 > 67.0 pg/ml. Indicators of the severity of coronary heart disease in women are anemia, leukocytosis and lymphocytopenia.

Conclusion:

1. Coronary heart disease without ST segment elevation in women occurs against the background of anemia and lymphocytopenia. Men are characterized by the absence of a connection between laboratory blood parameters and a shift in the ST segment.

2. In men with coronary heart disease, there is an increase in vascular endothelin factor in the blood by 1.12 times, IL-1 by 1.7 times.

3. The threshold level indicating the development of inflammation in coronary heart disease for both women and men is the concentration of IL-1 > 67.0 pg/ml.

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